

A MONITORING AND MANAGEMENT UTILITY FOR RAPIDIO CLUSTERS

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this project is to collect, organize, and display information about RapidIO nodes in the CERN Data Centre, as well as to provide a mechanism for issuing management commands to the cluster.

This project, done in collaboration between CERN openlab and IDT, is part of a larger effort to evaluate the feasibility of adopting the high-bandwidth, low-latency interconnect RapidIO for more widespread use at CERN for tasks such as data analysis and data acquisition.

Currently, to configure and gather information from a RapidIO cluster, it is necessary to issue commands to and print log files from each node individually. This is often done through writing custom scripts, but it can still be cumbersome to collect and format the information. The goal of this project is to allow a user to quickly read information and issue commands across a cluster, as well as provide a dashboard to visualize this information.

This first part of this project is a utility for issuing asynchronous commands across an entire cluster, supporting common operations like reading CPU and memory usage, as well as special operations for the RapidIO protocol. This interface, written in Node.js, is responsible for collecting, organizing, updating, and storing the data. The second part of the project is a static React dashboard for retrieving and visualizing the data.

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BACKGROUND

Ethernet is the networking backbone in data centres worldwide, yet for high-performance computing, RapidIO [1] is a technology that may offer lower latency and lower power consumption in certain use cases.

The CERN openlab program, together with collaboration partners, evaluates the feasibility of new technologies like RapidIO, under consideration currently for its potential to reduce latency of data analysis and data acquisition when coupled with frameworks widely used at CERN like ROOT [2]. For this project, IDT provided the technology and resources to evaluate the effectiveness of RapidIO.

WHAT IS RAPIDIO

RapidIO is an open-standard, packet-switched interconnect used to transmit data between endpoints in a network, providing high reliability and low latency. Depending on the application and circumstances, RapidIO may be more efficient than other interconnects like Ethernet. The RapidIO protocol is widely used in 4G/LTE base stations, as well as in other performance critical systems.

One of the primary advantages of RapidIO is zero-copy transfer, which removes an extra copy operation when transferring data to a remote host. In addition, RapidIO guarantees in-order packet delivery on the hardware level, a feature which removes the burden of detecting and retransmitting lost packets from the CPU. These benefits, combined with RapidIO's other CPU offloading features such as error correction at the hardware level, result in lower latency and less power consumption.

PROJECT GOALS

In a cluster of nodes, each one has properties critical to determining how a cluster is performing, such as CPU usage. There are also valuable properties special to the RapidIO protocol, like the memory amount and memory addresses reserved for the RapidIO kernel.

Currently, issuing the commands required to collect these properties from each node in a RapidIO cluster is often cumbersome, requiring multiple terminal sessions or writing a set of custom scripts. The intent of this project is to provide a quick way to read information about and issue commands to a cluster of RapidIO nodes through a monitoring and management utility. The goals of this project are as follows:

1. Develop a system for collecting, storing, and organizing data from the RapidIO cluster
2. Turn raw data into relevant insights about the cluster through an interface
3. Provide the ability to issue management commands to the cluster

CLUSTER CONFIGURATION

HARDWARE

The hardware setup includes a switch with four connected nodes.

- A Starbridge RapidExpress switch box, equipped with:
 - IDT CPS-1432 switch chip
 - 8 ports
 - nodes connected to the first 4 ports
- 4 RapidIO enabled PCs, equipped with:
 - PCIe to RapidIO bridge card
 - Intel Core i5 4440 CPU, 3.1 GHz
 - Linux Fedora 20, custom kernel based on v3.16.7

Figure 1: RapidExpress Switch with 4 RapidIO nodes

SOFTWARE

The RapidIO software is composed of Linux kernel drivers, as well as the RapidIO Remote Memory Access Platform (RRMAP) libraries [4] provided by IDT. Programs written in the user space access RapidIO operations through these RRMAP libraries, which interface the underlying kernel drivers.

Additionally, a technology called RIOSockets [5] has been developed by the Centaurus Computing team. The technology consists of a kernel module that implements the TCP/IP protocol over the RapidIO fabric, enabling the use of standard Berkeley socket interfaces.

OPERATIONS

Easing operations for managing the cluster is the focus of this project. Several of the most common management operations and data collection operations are described.

- **Power cycle the cluster.** This process of powering off and on the nodes is done by running a script from CERN's cluster management utility, *aiadm*. The *aiadm* credentials must be valid when this command is issued, which is done by requesting and renewing so called *Kerberos tickets*.
- **Enumerate the cluster.** The enumeration script is run from the master node and allows the nodes to discover each other on the network. This process also assigns each node a *destination_id*, a unique address for sending and receiving data.
- **Reading packet transmission information from the switch on behalf of each node.** Packet information can be recorded via the Fabric Management Daemon (FMD), accessible through a screen session on the master node.
- **Enabling and disabling RIOsockets.** RIOsockets is the technology RapidIO uses to interact over the TCP/IP protocol. It can be toggled by running a script on the master node. When enabled, the IP address can be found by running *ifconfig* and observing the *rsock0* interface.

TECHNOLOGIES CHOSEN

Node.js: Node is a JavaScript runtime environment for developing server-side applications, optimized for asynchronous operations with its non-blocking IO model. It is ideal for fetching data from multiple sources and managing a real-time web application.

React: A modular JavaScript framework developed by Facebook, allowing JavaScript elements to be compartmentalized into components. For this project, its modularity can be used to render many nodes in a cluster and update their states without repetitive code.

NPM: A dependency manager for Node.js.

React Bootstrap: A library for porting bootstrap UI components to React, used for elements like buttons and popovers.

Chart.js: An open-source graphing library for JavaScript, providing constructors for elegant, interactive graphs.

OpenStack: A cloud deployment service widely used at CERN, used to create a VM on which the application was deployed.

APPLICATION DESIGN

There are two separate parts of the application: a backend that manages data acquisition, organization, and management, and a frontend dashboard for visualizing the data.

BACKEND

The backend, written in Node.js, manages the data acquisition, organization, and storing.

1. Collecting Data

Each node has several properties that need to be collected from different places in the filesystem or are accessible through a different mechanism. For example, the *destination_id* address is simply found in the file:

```
/sys/class/rio_mport/rio_mport0/device/port_destid.
```

CPU utilization, by contrast, is found by using the *sysstat* package [6], which contains several utilities, including *sadf* and *sar*. Specifically, the *sadf* command is used to read utilization information generated by *sar*.

For packet information, a cron job reads packet information from the FMD screen session and stores the total packet transmissions for each 10-minute interval in the directory

```
/root/rapidio-monitor/logs/tx/stats-tx-{minute}
```

where *minute* is the last minute to write statistics for. Note that *tx* is used for transmitted packets, and a corresponding folder *rx* and file *stats-rx-{minute}* are used for storing received packets. This file structure allows the number of packets received and transmitted to be read easily from the directory for previous ten-minute intervals.

Originally, the data was collected synchronously, taking 8 seconds to collect from all 4 nodes. Rewritten asynchronously, the data can be retrieved from all nodes in less than a second.

The collected parameters are as follows, accessible through issuing a */fetch* command:

- *destination_id*: The unique identifier assigned to each node, used as the address for sending and receiving packets.
- *last_fetched*: The time at which the node information was last read.
- *cpu_utilization*: Includes idle, user, system, nice, steal, and iowait times, reported as an average over a 10 minute intervals.
- *load_averages*: The load on the CPU, reported as an average over 10 minute intervals.
- *rsock0*: Whether the RIOSockets interface is enabled.
- *rsock0_ip*: If RIOSockets is enabled, this is the IP address used to interact over TCP/IP.
- *mem_reserved*: The total memory amount and the addresses reserved for RapidIO .
- *mem_kernel*: The memory amount and the addresses reserved for RapidIO kernel drivers.
- *mem_sockets*: The memory amount and the addresses reserved for RIOSocket drivers.
- *lane_information*: The PCIe lane speed (Gbaud) and width per port. This dictionary also includes the throughput, which is calculated from the lane speed and width.

2. Storing Data

Several storage options were tested for data storage. Initially, MongoDB was used to store and update the data. The main drawback of this approach was that the entire database was overwritten with each collect operation, so it was inefficient. For now, the database is currently a custom-managed JSON file called *db.json*, located in the main directory of the *node-api* project. However, as more nodes are added to the cluster, it will be imperative to paginate the JSON file or switch to a more scalable database.

3. Cluster Management

The interface includes several commands for controlling and updating the state of the cluster. Commands are issued over HTTP and are executed by the *node-api* backend running on a virtual machine or locally. Note that localhost is unable to run the */powercycle* command, as explained below. The available commands are the following:

- */fetch*: runs scripts to collect data and update the database, fetching the parameters outlined in the Collecting Data section.
- */enumerate*: runs the enumeration script on the master node to assign each node a *destinationID* and make each node aware of each other.
- */powercycle*: runs a script on CERN's cluster management system, *aiadm* using Racktivity to turn off and on the nodes. This command requires authentication from Kerberos to run on *aiadm*. To refresh credentials, a cron job runs daily that runs a script to request new Kerberos credentials. This command cannot be issued locally since password-less authentication to *aiadm* is only possible via CERN Openstack VMs.
- */enableRsock*: runs a script on the master node to enable RIOSockets, assigning each node a RIOSockets IP address used for interacting over TCP/IP.
- */disableRsock*: runs a script of the master node to disable RIOSockets.
- */clear*: clears the database.

Many of the operations modify the data returned by the */fetch* call, and these automatically include a subsequent call to update the data automatically. For example, */enableRsock* subsequently calls the *node-api* *fetch* command to retrieve the newly assigned RIOSockets IP. Note that the */powercycle* command requires manually determining when the powercycle is complete and fetching the new data.

FRONTEND

Written in React, the frontend can be compiled and statically deployed. The dashboard compiles to static HTML, CSS, and JavaScript, making it convenient to deploy anywhere without a backend server.

1. Displaying Data

The dashboard pulls the data from the API, predominantly from the `/nodes` and `/packets` endpoints. The data is then channelled to its relevant components on the React dashboard.

For example, the CPU data is organized into a graph:

Figure 2: CPU usage graph

The reserved memory fields are displayed as a visualization like so:

Figure 3: Reserved memory visualization

2. Modular Components

One of the primary benefits of the React framework is its modularization of JavaScript. Each node in the cluster can be declared in a modular, re-usable way, allowing minimal redundancy. Notice the file structure on the left. The modularization allows for short, reusable code files.

Figure 4: Modular React components

3. State Management

The dashboard provides the ability to issue management commands, such as `/fetch` and `/enumerate` endpoints. These commands modify the state of the dashboard. React provides state management features, such that when the state of a master component is updated, it's children are redrawn.

The cluster was therefore designed with a top-down structure, such that all stateful properties were stored in the highest component (the App component) and functions to modify the state of the app were passed down the hierarchy. Thus, these functions will trigger redrawing of the appropriate components.

4. Configuration

The cluster topography (i.e. which node is connected to which port) is currently declared in a configuration file. Currently, it is also necessary to declare the master node, since some commands only work by running a script on the master. The configuration file also contains the number of ports on the switch. The configuration file is called `config.json` and is in the main directory of the `node-api` project.

```

config.json
{
  "nodes" : [
    {"name" : "gry05", "port" : 1, "sp" : 0},
    {"name" : "gry06", "port" : 2, "sp" : 4},
    {"name" : "gry07", "port" : 3, "sp" : 1},
    {"name" : "gry08", "port" : 4, "sp" : 5}
  ],
  "switch" : {
    "ports" : 8,
    "switchmodel" : "XFINITY",
    "master" : "gry05"
  }
}

```

Figure 5: Sample `config.json` file for 4 nodes

OUTCOME

The final product is a React dashboard and the JSON API that powers it. For example, a call to `/nodes` returns the following data. Note that the dictionaries for properties such as load averages and CPU utilization are collapsed for clarity.


```

[
  {
    "name": "gry05",
    "discovery_time": "Tuesday, August 15th, 2017, 3:50:07 PM",
    "operations": 9,
    "rsock0": false,
    "rsock0_ip": "",
    ▶ "mem_kernel": { ... }, // 3 items
    ▶ "lane_information": { ... }, // 2 items
    ▶ "mem_reserved": { ... }, // 3 items
    ▶ "mem_sockets": { ... }, // 3 items
    "destination_id": "0x0005",
    ▶ "load_averages": [ ... ], // 95 items
    ▶ "cpu_utilization": [ ... ] // 95 items
  },
  ▶ { ... }, // 12 items
  ▶ { ... }, // 12 items
  ▶ { ... } // 12 items
]

```

Figure 6: Sample API response for /nodes

The second part of the project, the dashboard, was completed and available on the CERN network. It can be seen below.

Figure 7: Completed dashboard, view of node gry06

Figure 8: Management commands and cluster status

Figure 9: Switch setup and port information

CONCLUSION

The purpose of this project was to create a tool to monitor and manage clusters of RapidIO nodes. The primary goals have been realized, and the dashboard and API are now deployed on CERN's Openstack infrastructure. In addition, the frontend is deployed internally using CERN's web services.

The codebase is modular and re-usable, and the frontend dashboard can be easily deployed on any other web hosting platform with simple static files. The backend must be deployed on a CERN virtual machine to access the internal network and retrieve information from the cluster.

Several optimizations have been made to minimize the time for fetching data like asynchronous operations, but more could be made in the future. Operations like power-cycle and enumeration take arbitrary amounts of time, during which the *fetch* operation may fail since the cluster is offline or busy. The current solution is implementing a delay, but implementing a startup script along with ping testing should be used to discover the exact time the cluster is back online.

Other features that could be added include the ability to adapt the topography to new cluster configurations without the use of a configuration file. In addition, the internal structures of switches could be visualized, along with packet overheads at each port, to find bottlenecks in the cluster.

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